

MODERN HEAT MADE ON THE BASIS OF LOCAL RAW MATERIALS INSULATION MATERIALS

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Annotation: The production of modern thermal insulation materials based on local raw materials, their widespread use in the construction of energy-efficient building solutions is one of the main tasks today.

Keywords : insulation, inorganic, organic, mineral, arbolite.

As a result of the ongoing reforms in the Republic, today the production of construction materials and products on the basis of local raw materials is expanding. In particular, the resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 23, 2019 No. PP-4335 "On additional measures for the accelerated development of the construction materials industry". According to this decision, the work to be done in the construction materials industry in 2019-2025 is specified [1].

From time immemorial, people have used many methods to heat their home, protecting the house from the cold. Our builders are carrying out a number of works on thermal insulation of walls, floors, roofs and facades in a modern way.

According to N.A.Mahmudova, "The lower the thermal conductivity, the more heat is stored, indicating that the general classification of thermal insulation materials is organic and inorganic [2].

Organic-based heat insulators are made on the basis of natural organic raw materials and synthetic polymers. Thus, organic-based thermal insulators include waste-based materials from the wood processing industry, waste paper (cellulose), sheep wool, cork, and some other natural materials [3]. However, all of them gradually absorb moisture, which can lose volume. They burn quickly, so they are rarely used in modern construction.

Let's take a look at how much or how little benefit polystyrene has to one of the most popular organic heaters currently in construction.

Expanded polystyrene began its journey as a thermal insulation material in the 1960s and has remained virtually unchanged since then. Polystyrene - is a housing made of polystyrene plastic mass filled with 98% air is a material used for, as a result of which it has high thermal insulation properties, as well as low weights, does not affect the shrinkage of the foundation and facilitates installation. Expanded polystyrene is a very convenient and popular insulation. However, it has a number of shortcomings, in particular:

- * relatively brittle;
- * flammable;
- * maydi cannot breathe, requires additional ventilation;
- * insects and rodents easily cross mazes and passages forms;
- * dries from direct sunlight and decomposes over time.

The use of inorganic insulation materials is often more effective than materials produced on the basis of local raw materials. The structure of inorganic thermal insulation materials has fibrous, open and closed pores. Organic materials often have an interconnected porous fibrous structure. Mineral cotton is a material that can be obtained by melting a mixture based soluble rocks (limestone, combustible slag) at a temperature of 1300-1400 °C and then turning it into fiber. Inorganic-based heaters include heat insulators that use minerals (stones, glass, metallurgical slag) for production. As result of spraying the dissolved mineral substance, mineral wool, which is one of the inorganic materials, is formed. It is widely used in many types of construction. The terminology includes all heaters consisting of fibers and reoresenting the class of mineral heaters in accordance with GOST standards. The properties of mineral wool are higher than those of organic materials:

Used as a unit of measurement of the heat retention capacity of wool:

- * sound insulation (keeps out sound);
- * good vapor permeability;
- * low flammability (can be used up to 650 °C);
- * contains no organic elements and prolongs service life.

It is also worth nothing that another type of thermal insulation is composite insulation, which is produced from raw materials on the basis of asbestos with the addition of thermal insulators-dolomite, vermiculite, perlite. Such materials demonstrate good thermal insulation properties, non-flammability, corrosion resistance, but asbestos insulation, like polystyrene, does not allow the passage of steam and air.

With the above, we can compare thermal insulators and analyze which insulation material will be of good quality and good in construction. When we compare the properties of arbolite and basalt fiber materials belonging to organic and inorganic bases, the thermal conductivity of arbolite is 0,08 (W/m°C), while the thermal conductivity of basalt fiber is 0,35 (W/m°C). We know that is equal to. In this case, we see that the thermal conductivity of basalt fiber is higher by a factor of 0,27 (W/m °C) compared to arbolite. Basalt fiber is an export-oriented building material. The Uzbek-British join venture Mega Invest Industrial LLC, which operates in Forish distict, is the only one in our country and Central Asia to produce a new type of construction material. The company has a production capacity of 2,500 tons of basalt fiber per year. According to experts, basalt is an environmentally friendly

product, it is 4 times lighter and 3 times stronger than steel reinforcement, 2 times cheaper, highly resistant to external influences and a completely stainless building material. Basalt fibers do not exceed 50 mm in length during production and are approximately 5:7 microns thick. For example, a wall measuring 3×5 meters . If we want to divide the room using, it must be wrapped in thermal insulation material. Let's assume that the price of 1 sq.m. of basalt fiber is 30,350 soums. If the area of the wall is 15 m², the cost of basalt fiber, which will cost 15m² to cover the wall, will be 455,250 soums. This allows the house to use less heat energy on cold days, which increases savings. Therefore, basalt is used in the production of various combustible fibers, tapes, plates from fibrous materials. The use of inorganic thermal insulation materials in construction can be considered the most effective. Their areas of application include: roof insulation, floor and floor insulation, building facades, ventilation ducts, space between rooms, cooling equipment surfaces, thermal insulation of sandwich panels, insulation of industrial equipment we can use.

In short, thermal insulation protects against the external effects of moisture and wind, helps people to use heating equipment less and is more cost-effective, protects against heat loss and provides better environmental benefits. In particular, investment projects for the production of construction materials are being implemented in Jizzakh region. In particular, a "Basalt Wool" specializing in the production of thermal insulation materials from 35,000 tons of basalt fiber per year will be results in the future.

References:

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